

Advancing Interdisciplinary Research: The European Centre of Excellence in Artificial Intelligence for Digital Humanities (CoE AI4DH)

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Abstract

This paper introduces the European Centre of Excellence in Artificial Intelligence for Digital Humanities (CoE AI4DH), a newly established EU-funded initiative based at the University of Ljubljana. The Centre addresses key scientific and structural barriers to interdisciplinary collaboration between computer science and the humanities, particularly in applying artificial intelligence (AI) methods to cultural, historical, and linguistic research. CoE AI4DH offers an integrated approach combining technical innovation with domain expertise, providing AI tools, research infrastructure, and training tailored to the needs of digital humanities and social science scholars. Key research activities include the development of NLP tools for historical texts, knowledge-enhanced large language models, and AI-supported media discourse analysis in low-resource languages. By fostering collaboration across disciplines, the Centre enables new forms of inquiry and promotes scalable, explainable, and ethically grounded AI applications. This contribution outlines the Centre’s mission, services, and research agenda, highlighting opportunities for international collaboration and shared innovation.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Digital Humanities; Social Sciences; AI4DH

1 Introduction

Unprecedented amounts of data are now available to researchers in the humanities and social sciences. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) is essential for processing these datasets, uncovering previously hidden patterns, and gaining insights at unprecedented speeds.

The inter-disciplinary collaboration between AI and the digital humanities remains a challenge. First, the expectations of the social sciences and humanities often do not match the possibilities of AI. Second, communication barriers arise

because experts from these fields often do not have a common vocabulary. Third, the organisational structures required for sustainable collaboration are weak. As a result, the potential of AI in the humanities often remains unrealised.

To overcome these obstacles, we have established the European Centre of Excellence in Artificial Intelligence for Digital Humanities (CoE AI4DH) as part of the EU-funded ERA Chair. The Centre is based at the Faculty of Computer and Information Science at the University of Ljubljana, and its mission is to empower digital humanities and social science researchers to apply state-of-the-art AI technologies, driving new discoveries and advancing knowledge in their fields.

The purpose of our presentation is to demonstrate the structure and goals of the CoE AI4DH, and to highlight the possibilities for participation and research collaboration.

2 The main activities of the European Centre of Excellence in Artificial Intelligence for Digital Humanities

For researchers in the humanities and social sciences, the CoE provides dedicated support for applying AI methods in both research and teaching. Scholars are encouraged to contact the Centre with specific questions or project needs. They will receive expert guidance on what is feasible, what existing tools and resources may be suited to their goals, and which challenges represent research gaps that could be addressed in collaboration with computer science experts at the CoE AI4DH.

The Centre's main activities focus on supporting interdisciplinary research and capacity building in the digital humanities. We provide AI research consultation, support the development and submission of joint project proposals, and host researchers working on their own projects. In addition, we create tools and open datasets, build and adapt large language models for applications in the digital humanities, and provide computational support to researchers. Finally, we offer AI training and education tailored to the digital humanities at MSc, PhD and micro-credential level.

2.1 Scope and services

Artificial intelligence offers powerful opportunities to advance research in the digital humanities by providing tools and methods that go far beyond traditional approaches. At CoE AI4DH, we use state-of-the-art AI technologies to support researchers in their exploration of complex cultural, historical and linguistic data. Specifically, we offer a wide range of resources and applications, including:

1. **Text analysis and natural language processing:** AI-powered tools can analyse and process vast amounts of textual data, helping researchers

uncover patterns, sentiment, and themes within literary works, historical documents, and other texts. Natural language processing algorithms can assist in translation, sentiment analysis, and topic modelling.

2. **Data mining and knowledge discovery:** AI algorithms can sift through datasets to identify relevant information, connections, and patterns. This is particularly useful for uncovering hidden relationships and trends within historical and cultural data.
3. **Image and multimedia analysis:** AI technologies, including computer vision, can support the analysis of images, videos, and other multimedia content. This includes identifying objects, recognising visual patterns, and creating searchable databases of visual resources.
4. **Digital archives and preservation:** AI can contribute to the digitisation and preservation of cultural heritage by automating image recognition, cataloguing, and metadata generation, supporting the creation and maintenance of digital archives.
5. **Machine learning for pattern recognition:** machine learning models can be trained to recognise patterns and trends in historical and cultural datasets, enabling new discoveries and insights that may not be evident through traditional methods.
6. **Interactive data visualisation:** AI can enhance data visualisation techniques, providing researchers with tools to create dynamic and interactive visualisations of cultural and historical data, improving communication and engagement with the audience.
7. **Automated transcription and translation:** AI-powered tools support the transcription of handwritten and historical documents, and translation into various languages, improving text accessibility.
8. **Collaborative research and crowdsourcing:** AI technologies can help automate routine tasks and support crowdsourcing initiatives, leading to more efficient and comprehensive data collection and analysis.
9. **Recommendation systems:** AI-based systems can suggest relevant literature, sources, or related work based on a researcher's interests and previous work.

Through these services, the Centre fosters collaboration across computer science, AI, linguistics, history, media studies, folkloristics, journalism, and philosophy. The AI approach is deeply interdisciplinary and adaptable, designed to integrate domain knowledge and support scholarly exploration with scientifically robust methods.

2.2 Research examples

Our current research covers a wide range of topics, including the development of natural language processing tools for analysing historical newspapers, comparative studies of historical newspaper collections, the creation of semantic and evaluation datasets from lexical resources, methods for injecting knowledge into large language models, AI infrastructure for data-driven folkloristics, procedures for explaining generative LLMs, and tools supporting social science analyses of media discourse in less-resourced languages.

This interdisciplinary collaboration has already led to significant results. For example, AI was used for the automatic detection of Cinderella-related motifs in folkloristic texts. Using a combination of machine learning and natural language processing, we identified motifs across an extensive collection of fairytales, and analysed their similarities through clustering and dimensionality reduction. This study demonstrates that large language models can capture complex semantic patterns within fairytale narratives, enabling scalable computational analysis across large data collections Arçon et al. [2025].

Another example is a study examining historical newspaper debates on women wearing trousers. In the 1890s, as the bicycle became popular in France, women began wearing trousers (known as bloomers), sparking a broader debate about women's clothes. Some newspapers of that time supported the new garment while others called for it to be banned. In August 1895, for example, Police Commissioner Lépine issued a decree after noticing that many women wore bloomers even if they did not own a bicycle; he therefore attempted to ban trousers outside cycling hours. In this study, AI tools were essential in analysing these debates, which would have been extremely difficult to locate and examine across vast historical newspaper archives using traditional methods (Omari [n.d.]; Tran et al. [2024]).

The Centre also provides high-performance computing infrastructure and expertise, supported by our partnership with Nvidia. This infrastructure enables the development and deployment of generative large language models tailored to the digital humanities. Our research agenda integrates scientific innovation with ethical reflection and technical rigour, aiming to develop AI tools that are explainable, fair, and aligned with scholarly values.

3 Conclusions

The European Centre of Excellence in Artificial Intelligence for Digital Humanities (CoE AI4DH) brings together expertise from computer science and the humanities to support the development of AI methods tailored to cultural, historical, and linguistic research. Its activities include providing research support, developing tools and datasets, training scholars, and building infrastructure to enable responsible, interdisciplinary work.

At the time of the proposed presentation, the Centre is in its first year of operation, focusing on establishing its infrastructure and educational programmes,

identifying shared research challenges, and initiating first collaborations. Information about the Centre’s ongoing activities and opportunities is available at ai4dh.eu

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